

Ref #	Authors	Title	Venue / Source	Year	Category
ref1	A. O. J. A. Sabriye and W. M. N. W. Zainon	An approach for detecting syntax and syntactic ambiguity in software requirement specification	Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology, vol. 96, no. 8	2018	NLP Tools
ref2	M. F. Zahrin, M. H. Osman, S. Hassan, A. Haron, and A. A. Halin	Ambiguity detection and improvement for Malay requirements specification: A systematic review	IJASEIT, vol. 13, no. 6	2023	NLP Tools
ref3	S. Gnesi and G. Trentanni	QuARS a NLP tool for requirements analysis	From Software Engineering to Formal Methods and Tools, and Back	2019	NLP Tools
ref4	S. Ezzini, S. Abualhaja, C. Arora, and M. Sabetzadeh	TAPHSIR: Towards anaphoric ambiguity detection and resolution in requirements	Proc. ACM ESEC/FSE '22	2022	NLP Tools
ref5	IBM	REAssistant IBM Engineering Requirements Quality Assistant	IBM Documentation	2023	Commercial Tool (ref only)
ref6	M. H. Osman and M. F. Zahrin	Ambi Detect: An ambiguous software requirements specification detection tool	Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education, vol. 12, no. 3	2021	NLP Tools
ref7	M. Riaz et al.	Automatic detection of ambiguous software requirements: An insight	5th International Conference on Information Management	2019	NLP Tools
ref8	T. Nakamichi, K. Nishiura, M. Sasakura, and A. Monden	An empirical study on ambiguous words in software requirements specifications of local government and library systems	22nd SERA	2024	Lexical Ambiguity
ref9	L. Beqiri, C. Montero, A. Cicchetti, and A. Kruglyak	Classifying ambiguous requirements: An explainable approach in railway industry	IEEE 32nd RE Workshops (REW)	2024	NLP Tools / Domain
ref10	X. Wu, C. Li, X. Wang, and H. Yang	A creative approach to reducing ambiguity in scenario-based software architecture analysis	Int. Journal of Automation and Computing, Springer	2018	Formal Languages
ref11	A. O. J. Sabriye and W. M. N. W. Zainon	A framework for detecting syntax and syntactic ambiguity in software requirement specification	8th ICIT, IEEE	2017	NLP Tools
ref12	F. Zait and A. Zarour	Addressing lexical and semantic ambiguity in natural language requirements	IEEE Conference paper	2018	NLP Tools
ref13	A. Ferrari, P. Spoletini, and S. Gnesi	Ambiguity cues in requirements elicitation interviews	Proc. RE 2016	2016	Interviews
ref14	K. H. Oo, A. Nordin, A. R. Ismail, and S. Sulaiman	An analysis of ambiguity detection techniques for software requirements specification (SRS)	Int. Journal of Engineering & Technology, vol. 7, no. 2.29	2018	NLP Tools / Ontology
ref15	F. de Bruijn and H. L. Dekkers	Ambiguity in natural language software requirements: A case study	REFSQ 2010, Springer	2010	Case Study
ref16	V. Jain, R. Malhotra, and S. Jain	Cross-domain ambiguity detection using linear transformation of word embedding spaces	Joint Proc. REFSQ-2020 Workshops	2020	NLP Tools
ref17	R. Lorch et al.	Formal methods in requirements engineering: Survey and future directions	Proc. IEEE/ACM FormalISE '24	2024	Formal Languages
ref18	F. Christophe, M. Wang, R. Coatanea, Y. Zeus, and A. Bernard	Grammatical and semantic disambiguation of requirements at elicitation and representation stages	Proc. ASME 2011 IDETC/CIE	2011	Formal Languages
ref19	H. Dar et al.	Gamify4LexAmb: A gamification-based approach to address lexical ambiguity in natural language requirements	PeerJ Comput. Sci., vol. 10, e2229	2024	Gamification
ref20	D. Firesmith	Generating complete, unambiguous, and verifiable requirements from stories, scenarios, and use cases	Journal of Object Technology, vol. 3, no. 10	2004	Scenarios / Use Cases
ref21	H. Dar	Reducing ambiguity in requirements elicitation via gamification	2020 IEEE 28th RE	2020	Gamification
ref22	H. Dar, S. Imtiaz, and M. Lali	Reducing requirements ambiguity via gamification: Comparison with traditional techniques	Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience, vol. 2022	2022	Gamification
ref23	A. Ferrari and S. Gnesi	Using collective intelligence to detect pragmatic ambiguities	20th IEEE RE	2012	Pragmatic Ambiguity
ref24	K. Aslam et al.	Detecting pragmatic ambiguity in requirement specification using novel concept maximum matching approach based on graph network	IEEE Access	2024	Pragmatic Ambiguity
ref25	U. Shah and D. Jinwala	Resolving ambiguities in natural language software requirements: A comprehensive survey	ACM SIGSOFT Software Engineering Notes, vol. 40, no. 5	2015	Survey
ref26	M. Alsaadi, A. Lisitsa, and M. Qasaimeh	Minimizing the ambiguities in medical devices regulations based on software requirement engineering techniques	DATA'19, Dubai	2019	Domain: Healthcare
ref27	E. Kempe, S. Semsar, A. Massey, S. Sampath, and C. Seaman	Modeling, analyzing and communicating regulatory ambiguity: An empirical study	MO2RE 2024 Workshop	2024	Domain: Legal
ref28	ISO/IEC 25010:2023	Systems and software engineering — SQuaRE — Quality-in-use model	ISO Standard	2023	Standard
ref29	A. Fantechi, S. Gnesi, and L. Semini	Ambiguity defects as variation points in requirements	VaMoS '17	2017	Ambiguity Types
ref30	A. Mahbub et al.	Can GPT-4 aid in detecting ambiguities, inconsistencies, and incompleteness in requirements analysis? A comprehensive case study	IEEE Access	2024	GenAI / LLM

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ref31	R. Izhar, S. Bhatti, and S. Alharthi	Bridging precision and complexity: A novel machine learning approach for ambiguity detection in software requirements	IEEE Access	2025	NLP Tools / ML
ref32	M. R. Asadabadi, M. Saberi, and E. Chang	A fuzzy game based framework to address ambiguities in performance based contracting	WI '17, Leipzig	2017	Rule-Based
ref33	M. R. Asadabadi, M. Saberi, O. Zwikael, and E. Chang	Ambiguous requirements: A semi-automated approach to identify and clarify ambiguity in large-scale projects	Computers & Industrial Engineering, vol. 149	2020	Rule-Based
ref34	M. S. Husain	Exploiting artificial immune system to optimize association rules for word sense disambiguation	IJISAE, vol. 9, no. 4	2021	NLP Tools
ref35	A. Ferrari and A. Esuli	An NLP approach for cross-domain ambiguity detection in requirements engineering	Automated Software Engineering	2019	NLP Tools
ref36	A. Bajceta, M. Leon, W. Afzal, P. Lindberg, and M. Bohlin	Using NLP tools to detect ambiguities in system requirements — A comparison study	NLP4RE 2022, REFSQ	2022	NLP Tools
ref37	F. R. Pereira, H. A. X. Costa, and P. A. Parreira	A comparative study of tools for anomaly detection in software requirements	Proc. XXIII SBQS '24	2024	NLP Tools
ref38	A. Rani and G. Aggarwal	Algorithm for automatic detection of ambiguities from software requirements	IJITEE, vol. 8, no. 9S	2019	NLP Tools
ref39	M. P. Buthelezi, J. van Der Poll, and E. O. Ochola	Ambiguity as a barrier to information security policy compliance: A content analysis	IEEE CSCI	2016	Domain: Software/Web
ref40	B. Gleich, O. Creighton, and L. Kof	Ambiguity detection: Towards a tool explaining ambiguity sources	Workshop paper	2014	NLP Tools
ref41	A. Ferrari, M. Fusani, and S. Gnesi	Are standards an ambiguity-free reference for product validation?	RSSRail 2017, Pistoia	2017	Templates / Standards
ref42	M. Osama, A. Zaki-Ismael, M. Abdelrazek, J. Grundy, and A. Ibrahim	Score-based automatic detection and resolution of syntactic ambiguity in natural language requirements	IEEE ICSME 2020	2020	NLP Tools
ref43	T. Kato and K. Tsuda	A method of ambiguity detection in requirement specifications by using a knowledge dictionary	26th KES 2022	2022	Ontology
ref44	N. Kiyavitskaya and N. Zeni	Requirements for tools for ambiguity identification and measurement in natural language requirements specifications	Requirements Eng., vol. 13	2008	Metrics / Measurement
ref45	A. K. Gupta and A. Deraman	A framework for software requirement ambiguity avoidance	IJECE, vol. 9, no. 6	2019	Frameworks
ref46	S. F. Tjong and D. M. Berry	Can rules of inferences resolve coordination ambiguity in natural language requirements specification?	11th WER 2008	2008	Pragmatic Ambiguity
ref47	J. S. Sinpang, S. Sulaiman, and N. Idris	Detecting ambiguity in requirements analysis using Mamdani fuzzy inference	Journal of Telecommunication, Electronic and Computer Engineering, vol. 9	2017	Rule-Based
ref48	T. T. Procko and O. Ochoa	An ontology based approach to the software engineering lifecycle: Application to software quality assurance in the aerospace industry	SSRN	N/A	Ontology / Domain: Aerospace
ref49	J. Feng, W. Miao, H. Zheng, et al.	FREPA: An automated and formal approach to requirement modeling and analysis in aircraft control	ACM ESEC/FSE 2020	2020	Domain: Aerospace
ref50	Y. Reich and E. Subrahmanian	Navigating complexity beyond collaborative design: The PSI network model and case studies	Research in Engineering Design, vol. 36, no. 4	2025	Domain: Aerospace
ref51	Z. Ma, C. Wen, J. Su, et al.	Towards practical requirement analysis and verification: A case study on software IP components in aerospace embedded systems	arXiv:2404.00795v1 [cs.SE]	2024	Domain: Aerospace
ref52	C. Arora et al.	Advancing requirements engineering through generative AI: Assessing the role of LLMs	Generative AI for Effective Software Development, Springer	2024	GenAI / LLM
ref53	M. Bragilovski, A. Van Can, F. Dalpiaz, and A. Sturm	Deriving domain models from user stories: Human vs. machines	IEEE 32nd RE	2024	Domain: Automotive
ref54	M. Dehn et al.	On identifying possible artificial intelligence applications in requirements engineering processes	Forsch Ingenieurwes, vol. 87	2023	Domain: Automotive
ref55	K. Khan et al.	Requirements engineering for automotive perception systems: An interview study	ACM REFSQ 2023	2023	Domain: Automotive
ref56	A. Mendes et al.	Model-driven systems engineering automation with artificial intelligence for robustly writing automotive system requirements	SAE Technical Paper 2025-01-8658	2025	Domain: Automotive
ref57	Z. Bencharqui et al.	Ontology-based requirements specification process	E3S Web of Conferences, vol. 351	2022	Ontology / Domain: Automotive
ref58	L. Mich and R. Garigliano	Ambiguity measures in requirements engineering	ICS2000, 16th IFIP World Computer Congress	2000	Metrics / Measurement
ref59	O. Seneviratne et al.	Explainability-driven quality assessment for rule-based systems	arXiv:2502.01253v1 [cs.AI]	2025	Domain: BFSI
ref60	J. Frattini	Identifying relevant factors of requirements quality: An industrial case study	ACM REFSQ 2024	2024	Domain: BFSI

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ref61	S. Abualhaija et al.	AI-enabled regulatory change analysis of legal requirements	Proc. RE 2024	2024	Domain: Legal
ref62	E. Guzman et al.	How do users like this feature? A fine grained sentiment analysis of app reviews	22nd RE	2014	Domain: Gaming
ref63	K. Zhou et al.	The evolving regulatory paradigm of AI in MedTech: A review of perspectives and where we are today	Therapeutic Innovation & Regulatory Science, vol. 58	2024	Domain: Healthcare
ref64	M. Deveci	Effective use of artificial intelligence in healthcare supply chain resilience using fuzzy decision-making model	Soft Computing	2023	Domain: Healthcare
ref65	V. Vyatkin	Software engineering in industrial automation: State-of-the-art review	IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics	2013	Domain: Industrial Auto.
ref66	C. K. Sahu, V. Rai, and V. Roshan	Well-formed quality of system requirements for verifying to ISO 29148-2018: An NLP-based framework and quantitative metric	Proc. ASME 2024 IDETC/CIE	2024	Metrics / NLP
ref67	INCOSE	INCOSE-TP-2003-002-05. Systems Engineering Handbook	John Wiley & Sons Ltd.	2023	Standard / Handbook
ref68	J. Xu et al.	Generative artificial intelligence in healthcare from the perspective of digital media: Applications, opportunities and challenges	Heliyon	2024	Domain: Healthcare
ref69	N. Singhal et al.	Generating clarification questions for disambiguating contracts	ACL LREC-COLING 2024	2024	Domain: Legal
ref70	A. Bajraktari et al.	Requirements engineering for research software: A vision	RE 2024 RE@Next! Papers	2024	Domain: Scientific Research
ref71	K. Pohl and C. Rupp	Requirements Engineering Fundamentals, 2nd ed.	Rocky Nook	2015	Book
ref72	S. Rahimi et al.	Requirement formalisation using natural language processing and machine learning: A systematic review	11th MODELSWARD 2023	2023	Domain: Software/Web
ref73	S. Basri et al.	Current trend of software requirement engineering process in IT small and medium enterprises (SMEs) — A systematic literature review	Proc. CITA	2023	Domain: Software/Web
ref74	J. Almonte et al.	Automated non-functional requirements generation in software engineering with large language models: A comparative study	IEEE CASCON 2025	2025	GenAI / LLM
ref75	K. Wiegers and J. Beatty	Software Requirements, 3rd ed.	Microsoft Press	2013	Book
ref76	R. Zrelli et al.	Natural2CTL: A dataset for natural language requirements and their CTL formal equivalents	REFSQ 2024, Springer, vol. 14588	2024	Rule-Based / Dataset
ref77	M. J. Page et al.	The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews	BMJ, vol. 372, n71	2021	Methodology (PRISMA)
ref78	M. E. Fagan	Design and code inspections to reduce errors in program development	IBM Systems Journal, vol. 15, no. 3	1976	Framework rationale
ref79	IEEE	IEEE Standard for Software Reviews and Audits (IEEE Std 1028-2008)	IEEE	2008	Standard
ref80	F. D. Davis	Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology	MIS Quarterly, vol. 13, no. 3	1989	Framework rationale